

Role of Insurance in Personal Financial Planning

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ABSTRACT:

The insurance sector used to be centered within the 12 months 1999 facilitating the entry of personal avid gamers in to the industry. With an annual progress fee of 24.31% and the most important no. Of lifestyles insurance policies in force, the abilities of the Indian coverage enterprise are colossal. Education on personal financial planning, financial security, financial independence, financial freedom, etc. is very essential. Also, there are various financial instruments available in the market for the customer to choose leading them to financial freedom. But, there is one particular tool called as life insurance that is vital for a long term financial planning.

Introduction: - Life insurance one of the fastest developing sectors in India given that 2000 as government allowed exclusive gamers and FDI as much as 26% and just lately cabinet accredited a thought to expand it to forty nine%. Life coverage in India was nationalized by using incorporating lifestyles coverage enterprise (LIC) in 1956. All personal life coverage companies at that time were taken over by LIC. In 1993, the government of India appointed RN Malhotra Committee to lay down a road map for privatization of the existence coverage sector.

Keywords: Insurance, IRDA, Mutual Fund, Personal Financial Planning

1. INTRODUCTION:

Financial planning is the process of developing a personal roadmap for your financial wellbeing. The inputs to the financial planning process are:

Your finances, i.e., your income, assets, and liabilities, your goals, i.e., your current and future financial needs and your appetite for risk.

The output of the financial planning process is a personal financial plan that tells you how to use your money to achieve your goals, keeping in mind inflation, real returns, and taxes. In short, financial planning is the process of systematically planning your finances towards achieving your short-term and long-term life goals.

2. OBJECTIVE:-

1. To gain knowledge of cognizance of coverage among men and women from Aundh Pune.
2. To understand realization among people about SIP and coverage.
3. To learn persons perception about Reliance coverage.
4. To grasp belief of individuals about coverage.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY: -

Study methodology system entails a no. of activities to be carried out. These are arranged in suitable sequence for tainting for conducting research.

1. Type of Research: Descriptive
2. Sampling Technique – Convenience sampling
3. Sample Size – 300

Data Collection:

1. Primary Data is used for the study. Data is collected through a questionnaire.
2. Secondary Data –Secondary data is also used for collecting company's information.

4. DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION:-

1. Do You Have A Life Insurance Policy Investment Plan?

TABLE No. 1

Insurance Investment Plans	No of Respondent's	%
Yes	250	90
No	50	30
Total	300	120%

CHART No.1

Interpretation:

Among 300 respondents 200 respondents already have insurance policy against their name while 50 respondents do not.

2. Which Insurance Plans Do You Know?

TABLE No.2

Name of Insurance Plan	No. of Respondent	%
Term insurance Plan	35	20%
Endowment Plan	165	60%
ULIP	85	30%
Don't know	15	10%
Total	300	120%

CHART 2

Interpretation:

Among 300 respondents 165 knows only endowment plans, 85 knows ULIP, 35 term insurance and only 15 are unaware of insurance plans

3.Which According To You Is An Ideal Policy Term?

TABLE 3

AGE GROUP	NO.OF RESPONDENTS	%
18-25 YEARS	128	50%
26-35YEARS	72	30%
36-49 YEARS	53	20%
50-60YEARS	32	12%
MORE THAN 60 YEARS	15	8%
TOTAL	300	120%

CHART 3

Interpretation:

The survey of Age is numbers of Respondents it is clear that 50% growth has come in 18 to 25 years from the vision of Globalization in life insurance industry.

1. Gender Classification Of Surveyed Respondents

TABLE 4

PARTICULAR	NO OF RESPONDENTS	%
MALE	204	85%
FEMALE	96	35%
TOTAL	300	120%

CHART 4

Interpretation:

Under gender categorization majority male respondents 204, while 96 are female insurance seekers.

5. What Kind Of Insurance Policy Would Suits You Best In Your Current Stage Of Life?

TABLE 5

TYPE PLAN	NO OF RESPONDENTS	%
TERMS INSURANCE PLAN	105	45%
ENDOWMENT PLAN	120	50%
PENSION PLAN	25	10%
CHILD PLANS	20	5%
TAX SAVING PLAN	30	10%
TOTAL	300	120%

CHART 5

Interpretation:

Above analysis shows that 50% respondents are interested to opt for endowment plans while 45 % for term insurance plan.

5. FINDINGS:

1. The collected data has been compiled and analyzed in various angles.
2. Among 300 respondents 250 respondents already have insurance policy against their name while 50 respondents do not.
3. Among 300 respondents 165 knows only endowment plans, 85 knows ULIP, 35 term insurance and only 15 are unaware of insurance plans
4. The survey of Age is numbers of Respondents it is clear that 50% growth has come in 18 to 25 years from the vision of Globalization in life insurance industry.
5. Under gender categorization majority male respondents 204, while 96 are female insurance seekers.
6. Above analysis shows that 50% respondents are interested to opt for endowment plans while 45 % for term insurance plan.

6. SUGGESTION:

1. The company has superb recognition within the metropolis but nonetheless an extraordinarily massive subject which are not aware about the company, so I want to advocate that company should promote in that subject about their offerings. The enterprise can broaden awareness from hoardings in small villages and cities.
2. Limitations: -
3. To carry out the research gain knowledge of the next boundaries were expected & faced in the course of the study learn.
4. Pattern dimension may not special consultant universe there may be likelihood of some error to a restrained extent.
5. Limited time interval; available best two months (June to August)
6. Administration would possibly not like to share their views on the topic

7. CONCLUSION:

The research conducted through me is summarized as under:

From the research, we can say that Role of Insurance in Financial Planning is Important. The average person can, today, expect to live a healthy life well into his or her seventies or eighties, which means that retirement life is almost as long as working life. Financially, it implies that savings (after taking into account inflation) should be enough, not just to maintain the same lifestyle for almost 25-30 years, with no new income, but also to take care of medical expenses, which are usually high the older a person gets. Planning for all this is a tall order for anyone. That's why it's critical for everyone to plan their finances from an early age. We might be concluded that Reliance in all ways as when put next with the other has very good scope within the pune city. It supplies fluctuate excellent services to their consumers. Reliance in all methods is excellent; simply that it wants to furnish more and better offerings and fast offerings to the purchasers

8. REFERENCES:

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